

The Long Wait

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By Donward Caniete Bughaw

Besides the extreme heat of the hot, glowing coals coming out of the glass wall and the thick stack of smoke oozing from the chimney, everyone seemed to be enjoying the view how the chickens were roasted with its own fats and juices, circulating and exposing the meat to the heat with the rotary grill. Everybody wants a piece of roast chicken for dinner at home.

It was the night before Christmas and I was standing silently next to the crowd of people gathering around the rotisserie, waiting patiently for my turn and the queue to immerse. For a couple of minutes, a mid-thirty woman wearing a piece of white sleeveless and short finally spotted me.

"Want a piece of roast chicken, sir?" She asked, motioning the pen she's holding towards the direction of the spit.

"Yes, madame," I replied.

"You are?"

"Mr. Bughaw."

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"One hundred eighty five pesos," she demanded and wrote my name on the notebook she's holding.

I took one greenish paper bill from my wallet and handed it to her. She took it and handed me the change.

"Are all those roast chickens already taken?" I asked seeing the chickens on one of the spit almost roast.

"We're sorry to tell you that those chickens we're already taken. But the other one still don't have. If you can wait, you can have it at nine."

"Oh, sure.," I responded. "Which one?"

"In that spit," she said pointing her fingers to the newly exposed chicken rotisserie.

For a moment, I left the rotisserie and went to the nearby street food booths where I left my girlfriend. I found her there still seated on the wooden bench, right where I left her, busy tapping the phone's screen.

"How are you?" I asked her.

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She stopped tapping the screen of her phone for a moment and looked at me. "I'm perfectly fine. How about you?"

I just lit a smile and told her about the roast chicken. "The order will took us a long wait.

"Oh. That's definitely a challenging part where you're patience is measured," she commented. "What had the seller told you?"

"Almost chickens on the spit are already taken."

"And so?"

"We can have ours at nine."

She took a glance over her phone. "It's still 7:35. It really seems to be a long wait for us. Why don't you take a seat for a moment?"

"Not necessarily. I need to go back there so I can keep an eye on the chicken."

"Okay."

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And so I took my leave and went back to the rotisserie again. And it took less than an hour when I saw how the pale dressed chickens on the spit started to turned red. Excitement peaks and the sound of the fatty liquid dripping on burning embers somehow adds the thrill I felt. It took another couple of minutes when the chickens were finally roasted and was taken away from the grill.

The butler put on his apron and started removing the chickens from the spit using a kitchen knife. Everyone held their breath as they watched the butler chopped the roast chickens. One by one, the roast chickens were chopped and those who received the prize left the rotisserie in excitement. Not until only one remains.

I lit a smile. Finally, I can have it with me now.

The butler started chopping the last roast chicken. The sound of the kitchen knife that hit on the chopping board as the chicken was chopped began to grow louder and faster in my ear. This somehow adds the excitement and the thrill I felt.

As soon as the butler finished chopping the roast chicken, he had it packed on a black cellophane. My hands were fidgeting next to the loud pounding of my heart. I am really about to take the chicken with me. However, the excitement that I felt and the sweet smile plastered on my face faded. I don't know what to say. Sweats began gliding down, wetting my entire body. An aged woman came and took over the claimed for my roast chicken instead.

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